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SOCIAL SCIENCES

Education & Educational Research

СОЦІАЛЬНІ НАУКИ

Освіта та педагогічні дослідження

SOCIAL SCIENCES. Education & Educational Research

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Preparation of Future Specialists of the Social Sphere for the Formation of a Healthy Lifestyle of Pupils in the Professionally-Directed Educational Environment

Author's Contribution:

A – Study design;
B – Data collection;
C – Statistical analysis;
D – Data interpretation;
E – Manuscript preparation;
F – Literature search;
G – Funds collection

Kostina V. V.¹ ABCDEFG¹ H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, Ukraine**Received:** 25.08.2019; **Accepted:** 22.09.2019; **Published:** 30.11.2019**Background and
Aim of Study:****Abstract**

Preparing future social pedagogues and social workers for prevention activities with students in general and forming healthy lifestyles in particular is an important task of modern professional education of social specialists.

The aim of the study: to determine the effectiveness of the impact of the developed scientific and methodological support of the process of training future specialists in the social sphere to form a healthy lifestyle of students on indicators of their personal and professional potential.

Material and Methods:

The following complex of theoretical research methods has been used: analysis, comparison, generalization, systematization literature and interpretation of results. Methods of mathematical statistics have been used. The use of the Pearson criterion χ^2 in the statistical processing of experimental data in groups E_1 and K_1 (students of H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University) allowed to determine a significant difference in the readiness of future specialists of the control and experimental groups after the experiment and to prove the effectiveness of the experimental work.

Results:

The article revealed the components of the process of professional training of future specialists in the social sphere to work on the formation of healthy lifestyles of students, as well as the peculiarities of its organization in the various social institutions that carry out the function of preventing their maladjustment.

Conclusions:

The analysis of the results of the experimental study on the problem of preparing future specialists in the social sphere to form a healthy lifestyle of pupils allowed to draw the conclusions about efficiency of an experimental study on the formation of health-saving readiness of future social pedagogues and social workers in the conditions of state and non-governmental social institutions of the network of social care institutions affiliated with Higher Education Institutions.

Keywords:

professional training, future specialists in the social sphere, prevention of maladjustment of students, forming a healthy lifestyle, professionally-oriented educational space, social institutions.

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Introduction

Given the proliferation of aggression, bullying, various addictions in the environment of children and young people, the problem of preventing maladjustment of students in recent years has become extremely urgent, which necessitates the active search for effective ways to prepare future professionals in the social sphere to form a healthy social life of students. Preparing future social pedagogues and social workers for preventative activities with students in general and shaping healthy lifestyles in particular is an important task of modern professional education for social specialists, so it needs to take into account the requirements of the present (formation of humanistic orientation of actions and professional behavior, decisions, readiness to work in crisis situations, etc) during its implementation.

The realization of the above requirements is possible during the organization of the process of professional training of future social pedagogues and social workers in the conditions of professionally-oriented educational space, which provides conditions for conducting training sessions, practices and student scientific researches at the institutions of higher education and institutions partnering with it, that conduct work on prevention of maladjustment of students.

The analysis of the scientific literature showed that the researchers studied the following aspects of the problem of professional training of future social pedagogues and social workers to prevent maladjustment of students: features of interaction of social pedagogues with older adolescents who are prone to manifestations of addictive behavior; the formation of healthy lifestyles of students; technological and methodological support for the prevention and correction of adolescent addictive behavior in the work of social pedagogues of different social institutions; formation of specialists' readiness for preventive work with high school students; preparation of future social pedagogues and social workers for preventive work with students with deviant behavior; preparation of future social pedagogues for preventive activity in educational and training institutions. However, despite the great variety of research works, the problem of training future specialists in the social sphere to form a healthy lifestyle students under partnership of different social institutions is underdeveloped, lacks its scientific and methodological support, which would fully ensure professional self-determination and self-improvement of future specialists in the indicated direction.

The aim of the study. To determine the effectiveness of the impact of the developed scientific and methodological support of the process of preparation of future specialists in the social sphere for the prevention of maladjustment of students, the introduction of which allowed to develop a special professional competence to form a healthy lifestyle of students in the conditions of created professionally-oriented educational space, on the indicators of their professional personal potential.

The objectives of the article are: characterization of the components of content and features of preparation of future social pedagogues and social workers to work on the formation of healthy lifestyles of students in different social institutions as a basis for preventing their

maladjustment, as well as an experimental study of the impact of the developed methodological support on the indicators of their personal and professional potential.

Materials and Methods

The following complex of theoretical research methods has been used: analysis, comparison, generalization, systematization literature and interpretation of results. Methods of mathematical statistics have been used. The use of the Pearson criterion χ^2 in the statistical processing of experimental data in groups of students of H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University allowed to determine a significant difference in the readiness of future specialists of the control and experimental groups after the experiment and to prove the effectiveness of the experimental work.

Analyzing and summarizing the results of research and teaching practice has made it possible to argue that the role of social institutions in preventing the phenomenon of social maladjustment of students is crucial, so preparing future professionals in the social sphere to perform a preventive function is an important task of professional education. So, Lodkina (2009) proposes the introduction of schools of socio-ecological approach, which provides three areas: childhood ecology, family ecology and society ecology – which allows to create an educational environment that provides priority to the values of life, health and development of the child. The scientist notes that among the leading directions in work with children are: identification of children in the risk zone, identification of causes that lead to child maladjustment, as well as prevention in them of manifestations of deviant behavior, formation in students need for a healthy lifestyle (Lodkina, 2009, p. 82).

An important aspect in preparing future professionals in the social sphere for the prevention of maladjustment of students is to study the characteristics of psychological characteristics of children and young people who are prone to manifestations of deviant behavior. Thus, Malykhina (2012, p. 46) states that when looking for ways to prevent adolescent immoral acts, it is important to “pay attention to the individual, in all the variety of characteristics”. The scientist has determined the general psychological conditions for preventing immoral acts that affect the effectiveness of the entire educational process with adolescents in school (Malykhina, 2012, p. 89): timely diagnosis of immoral behavior of adolescents; formation of consciousness and self-consciousness, which determines the correct attitude to moral norms; development of a positive motivations and needs sphere of adolescent personality; establishing a trusting relationship between the caregiver and the pupil.

Based on the ideas of the aforementioned scientists, we introduced a supplement to the content of the training of future specialists in the social sphere during the acquisition of the special course “Social work on forming a healthy lifestyle”, which allows to increase the indicators of their personal and professional potential regarding the basics of diagnosing problems and difficulties of socialization of children and youth that lead to the development of maladjustment, by getting acquainted with the methods of creating and

using in the work of a social pedagogue of the general secondary education institution a student "health passport" and methods of formation of healthy lifestyles in terms of various social institutions.

Researchers have shown that the occurrence of various deviations in students' behavior is much easier to predict and create conditions for their avoidance than to later make efforts to correct them. Thus, Korchova (2007, pp. 48–49) developed a structural-logical model of prevention of sexual deviance of high school students, which reflects the system of preventive work, which is a specific subsystem in the general system of school work. The scientist argues the need for the formation of sexual culture of high school students (Korchova, 2007, pp. 55–58), which contains the following components (cognitive: knowledge of the basics of a healthy lifestyle, the idea of human sexuality; emotional-volitional: willingness to master inter-gender skills, behavioral: compliance with the rules and rules of sexual culture). The researcher defined the following criteria (physiological culture, psychological culture, ethical culture, social culture) and indicators (physical development, awareness of sexual physiological functions of the human body, abandonment of bad habits; correspondence of sexual life to actual age, formation of morally-acceptable intercourse between sexes, the formation and priority of human values, the presence of a positive ideal, the understanding of socially-acceptance forms of sexual relations, formed social responsibility, responsible attitude for the destiny of another person, formed vision of the future family) formation of high-value social motives of high school students, aimed at preserving and strengthening the sexual culture, self-education skills, positive moral attributes.

The researcher also determined the conditions that ensure the effectiveness of the school of formation of sexual culture of high school students (Korchova, 2007, pp. 137–138): improving the quality of upbringing and education of high school students, taking into account their individual and age characteristics of psychosocial development and use of educational interactive technologies; providing pedagogical personnel with the latest pedagogical technologies, forms and methods of forming the sexual culture of high school students, introducing them into the practice of comprehensive educational institutions; organization of purposeful scientific and practical work with parents through psychological-communicative trainings, discussions, lectures, role-playing games, problem seminars, seminars-workshops using interactive forms and teaching methods; formation of high-motivated high school students for healthy lifestyle and sexual culture. Considering the above conditions in the preparation of future social pedagogues will allow timely detection and prevention of the spread of sexual deviance among students.

The influence of social and pedagogical activity on educational, physical cultural and healthy work on the formation of the health culture of schoolchildrens and students was studied by Melnyk (2017, 2019).

Fetisova (2014) proposes to use the following preventive tools for the work of a social pedagogue with

"difficult children" who have suicidal tendencies: trainings to get out of difficult life situations, identify abilities and interests, communicate with teenagers about plans for the future, etc. We consider it necessary to familiarize future social pedagogues and social workers with the peculiarities of using the above-mentioned means in preventive work with students who are prone to suicidal behavior, which will improve their professional health-saving competence.

One of the important problems in the work of social workers is prevention of child neglect in Ukraine. Orzhekhovskaya (2009, p. 6) identifies the following strategic directions of its decision: 1) creation of such preventive space for the child and such educational system at school, which would prevent alienation of pupils from the educational institution, ensure a positive microclimate in the school teams, facilitate the acquisition of specific preventive methods by subject teachers, classroom leaders, deputy directors of educational work, school psychologists, social pedagogues; the need to consolidate the efforts of the school, law enforcement agencies, NGOs, religious denominations, work with parents; 2) implementation of measures to adapt and re-socialize street children by introducing ... alternative forms of education and upbringing ... maximizing the use of social rehabilitation schools; 3) providing training for the prevention of child neglect.

Analysis of the research of Ternovets (2013, pp. 50–52) showed that among the effective forms of preparation of future social pedagogues for the prevention of social orphanage in school the following were identified: workshop "Creating a data bank of innovative social and pedagogical experience", video lectures "Modern pedagogical technologies to prevent the emergence of social orphans", trainings "Psychology of pedagogical communication" (for social pedagogues); research work (participation in conferences, olympiads, competitions of student scientific works, projects, grants of the Department of Social Pedagogy of Shevchenko LNU), talks, consultations, round tables, etc (for future social pedagogues). Given the above ideas of researchers, it is important in the preparation of future social pedagogues and social workers to create conditions for organizing continuous interaction of social work students with pupils deprived of parental care and prone to vagrancy, who are the pupils of specialized institutions (psychologists, social rehabilitation centers working with young people who are addicted to narcotic substances, etc) during the acquisition of variant special courses, training and on-site practice during 3-5 years of study and participation in research.

As Kyrychenko and Kovganich (2009, p. 7) point out, "the attribute of an innovative educational institution of the 21st century becomes an educational space that is opened, aimed at fostering a child as a subject of one's own life and success, and mastering one's vital competence". Researchers define the principle of "preventive" as one of the leading principles of construction of educational space (transformation of risk environment into space of opportunities for self-realization of a child's personality makes it possible to significantly increase the efficiency of educational

work, to prevent the spread of negative phenomena in the child and youth environment) (Kyrychenko & Kovganich, 2009, p. 9). Scientists have identified the following methodological tools that will allow to solve effectively the problems of educational space (Kyrychenko & Kovganich, 2009, pp. 10–11): reorganized councils of student self-government; special subjects or elective courses that promote self-development of the individual; an extensive network of circles and clubs for the sake of pre-vocational training and vocational guidance; children's and youth non-governmental organizations. The use of the ideas of Kyrychenko and Kovganich (2009) in the professional training of future specialists in the social sphere made it possible to substantiate the need to form their willingness to organize complex health-saving activities at all levels of interaction of specialists in the environment of a certain social institution: in the context of student self-government and social services, in terms of professional interaction with parents and students, in terms of professional interaction with colleagues from different social institutions and during scientific research. Analysis and generalization of the results of the research by Pykhtina and Novhorodskyi (2007, p. 11) allowed to identify groups of children who are prone to maladjustment: school-age children not attending school; orphans; socially-orphaned children; adolescents using drugs and toxic substances; adolescents with sexually explicit behavior; teenage offenders. We consider it necessary to acquaint future specialists in the social sphere with the above-mentioned classification of pupils in order to determine the features of preventive work with vulnerable categories of student youth.

Among the important directions of early prevention of social and pedagogical neglect of the child, the researchers identify the following (Pykhtina & Novhorodskyi, 2007, pp. 20–25): 1) humanization of the educational process through the introduction of innovative pedagogical technologies in the educational environment developing healthy lifestyle values; expansion of leisure activities; creation and introduction of technologies of early diagnostics of various forms of deviant behavior); 2) improving family relationships through outreach to parents, working with families at risk); 3) assisting the individual in self-improvement and self-realization through preventive training and education.

Familiarization of future specialists in the social sphere with the abovementioned conditions, which provide full socialization and individualization of the child's personality, will allow to carry out preventive activities in the educational environment comprehensively and to ensure the elimination of negative factors at different levels (personal, micro-environment and environment). To carry out prevention activities with students, Pykhtina and Novhorodskyi (2007, pp. 170–171) propose to use a model that combines four components of the pedagogical model of prevention: 1) information; 2) education; 3) an alternative that will allow us to form an adequate self-esteem and feel useful in society; 4) interventions (specialist consultations, helpline, peer coaching, creation of new communication groups, etc).

We consider it necessary to acquaint future professionals in the social sphere who carry out preventive work with students, with the proposed model during the acquisition of the special course “Designing social and educational environment”, which will enhance their professional competence in this direction. Given that negative effects such as aggression and bullying have become widespread in the student environment, work to prevent child abuse is an important area of social work to prevent students from maladjustment. Analysis of the results of the research of Panchenko (2013) allowed to identify in the content of social and pedagogical work of general secondary education institutions and other social institutions three types of prevention of child abuse: primary (informing children and young people from prosperous families about legal norms and real life situations regarding abuse); secondary (group work with children, parents of “at-risk” families to build knowledge and life skills needed to protect against violence, as well as establishments that assist victims of violence through training, information, clarification, etc); tertiary (mainly provided in shelters, specialized institutions for children and young people, who are prone to risky behavior through consultations and peer and self-help groups). The researcher (Panchenko, 2013, pp. 42–46) also singled out the features and suggested different forms and methods of preventive work with parents, children, teachers and in the environment (lectures, parent universities, parental meetings, trainings, etc). Familiarization of future social pedagogues and social workers during the practice-oriented training on the basis of partnership with Higher Education Institutions network with the essence and peculiarities of work on the prevention of abuse of children ensures the acquisition by future specialists of special professional competence in the specified direction while studying subjects such as “Technology of social and pedagogical work”, “Technology of social work abroad”, “Social and rehabilitation work in specialized institutions”.

Training of future specialists in higher education institutions was studied by Melnyk and Pypenko (2018). An analysis of the results of Predborskaja's (2006, p. 15) research showed that “contemporary changing reality requires probabilistic thinking: the complication of things requires the complication of mental structures, which, in turn, implies corresponding changes in the content and methods of teaching”. Taking into account the ideas of the researcher, in the process of professional training of future specialists in the social sphere to work on the prevention of maladjustment of students during the mastering of the discipline “Ethnopedagogy” there were used innovative experience, new forms and methods of social work with vulnerable contingents in order to develop in students probabilistic thinking and the means to work in a changing world, to enable them to adapt professionally in their learning and professional development (Kostina, 2018b).

Analysis and synthesis of scientific studies on the philosophy of education showed that among the problems of modern professional education, scientists see the low level of general methodological training of future professionals and suggest introducing special

courses in philosophy of life to improve the characteristics of the pedagogical process (Korotiaiev, Kurylo, & Savchenko, 2010). To increase the level of preparedness of future specialists in the social sphere to work on the formation of healthy lifestyles of students, we introduce them to the philosophical foundations of health care activities as a basis for forming their professional outlook while mastering the discipline “Social work for preservation and promotion of health”.

Results

Based on the above ideas of scientists, with the aim of increasing the effectiveness of professional training of future social pedagogues and social workers to prevent maladjustment of students, the formation of their special competence to form a healthy lifestyle of students through the implementation of complex professional health saving activities of various specialists in the field of coordination of specialists in the system of various social institutions we have developed such scientific and methodological support (Kostina, 2016, 2017, 2018a, 2018b): training manual “Theory and Practice of Ethno-Pedagogical Means in Professional Training of Social Workers to Prevent Maladjustment of Students”, “Curricula and Methodological Support for Special Courses for Future Social Pedagogues and Social Workers”, “Designing a social and educational environment for students”, “Social work on forming a healthy lifestyle”, methodical materials to ensure the passage of social and pedagogical practice in the Institutions of Secondary Education and social services, the introduction of training “Professional skills of a specialist in the field of work with vulnerable contingents”, methodological materials for the preparation of scientific studies on social pedagogy and social work on the problem of prevention of maladjustment of students. With the introduction of the above-mentioned methodological support in the process of preparing future social pedagogues and social workers, an enriched professionally-oriented educational space was created, the presence of which made it possible to realize certain components that make up the content of professional readiness of future specialists in the social sphere to form a healthy lifestyle; locate student in the “risk zone”; identify the causes that lead to maladjustment of students; prevention of students’ divergent behaviors through multi-level and multi-directional activities to help students develop healthy lifestyle needs and develop healthy lifestyle skills.

In order to create a professionally-oriented educational space during the experimental study, cooperation agreements were concluded between H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University with Kharkov Pedagogical Lyceum No. 4, Kharkiv High School

No. 36, Kharkiv Gymnasium No. 43, Kharkiv Specialized School of I-III Grades No. 134 of Kharkiv City Council of Kharkiv Region, CSSFCY of Kyiv and Kholodnogorsk districts of Kharkiv, The Kharkiv Regional Center for Social and Psychological Rehabilitation of Children and the Municipal Community Center for Kharkiv Regional Center for Social and Psychological Rehabilitation of Children “Harmony”, by the Community Service and Social Services Charitable organization “Caritas-Kharkiv”, by “Kharkiv Charitable Foundation Blago”, Kharkiv Regional Public Organization “Culture of Health”, Sector of Juvenile Probation in Kharkiv, a branch of the State Institution “Probation Center” in Kharkiv region, which provided opportunities for professionalization of future social pedagogues and social workers of the experimental group in the direction of forming a healthy lifestyle of students during the organization of training sessions, educational events, practices and conducting scientific research on mentioned topics.

Future social pedagogues and social workers, during the experimental study, had the opportunity not only to get acquainted with the theoretical bases of health-saving activities with students, but also to learn the practice of preventive health-saving activities during direct interaction with leading specialists of the social sector and in different social institutions (general secondary education institutions, centers for social and psychological rehabilitation for children, CSSFCY, community organizations, etc). An important aspect of their professional training was learning the experience of partnerships between specialists of different social institutions in order to solve students’ problems and prevent their maladjustment (Kostina, 2018a, pp. 142–147). Among the interesting experiences of interaction with students belonging to vulnerable contingents, accumulated by future social pedagogues and social workers, it is worth mentioning the carrying out of educational activities for the formation of healthy way of life for students displaced from the ATO zone on the basis of COCF “Caritas-Kharkiv”, Republican prophylactic quest from COKhCF “Blago”, organization of preventive measures for children deprived of parental care, on the bases of centers for social and psychological rehabilitation of children and the sector of juvenile probation of the city of Kharkiv and others.

The analysis of the results of the experimental study revealed the positive dynamics of indicators of personal and professional potential of future specialists in the social sphere compared with the results of measurements in the control group (see Table 1), which allowed to confirm the effectiveness of the developed scientific and methodological support.

Table 1. Dynamics of formation of future social educators and social workers readiness for prevention of students’ maladaptation (%).

Levels of manifestation	The beginning of the experiment		End of experiment	
	E ₁	K ₁	E ₁	K ₁
Professionally specialized	0.0	0.0	31.6	10.5
Professionally qualified	26.3	31.6	42.1	31.6
Primary	39.5	57.9	26.3	57.9
Insufficient	34.2	10.5	0.0	0.0

Statistical processing of data using Pearson's criterion χ^2 to check the homogeneity of distribution between groups E_1 and K_1 after forming the experimental part

made it possible to determine that there is a statistical difference between samples E_1 and K_1 , which is evidence of its effectiveness (see Table 2).

Table 2. Statistical verification of experimental study results using the Pearson criterion χ^2 .

Groups		P-value before experiment	Statistical difference between groups	P-value after experiment	Statistical difference between groups
E	K				
E_1	K_1	6.271 < 7.378	Absent	9.071 > 7.378	Exists

Discussion

The analysis of scientific researches on the problem of professional training of future social pedagogues and social workers for the prevention of students' maladjustment showed that the following ideas were offered by scientists: creation of conditions for development of skills and abilities for preventive work in the child and youth environment (Fetisova, 2014; Korchova, 2007; Lodkina, 2009; Malykhina, 2012; Melnyk, 2017, 2019; Panchenko, 2013; Pykhtina & Novhorodskiy, 2007; Ternovets, 2013); formation in future specialists of philosophical basis for effective realization of future professional activity (Korotiaiev, Kurylo, & Savchenko, 2009; Kyrychenko & Kovhanych, 2010; Melnyk & Pypenko, 2018; Predborskaja, 2006). The conducted researches have allowed to confirm the importance of the ideas proposed by the author regarding the influence of the developed professional and educational environment on the indicators of the personal and professional potential of future social pedagogues and social workers.

Conclusions

The analysis of the results of the experimental study on the problem of preparing future specialists in the social sphere to form a healthy lifestyle of pupils allowed to draw the following conclusions: 1) programs of professional disciplines and programs of practice of students of 1-6 years of study with questions concerning preservation and promotion of health of pupils; introduction of the training "Professional skills of a specialist in the field of work with vulnerable contingents"; development and implementation of a special course "Social work on forming a healthy lifestyle"; 2) increasing motivation and interest in the prevention of students' maladjustment in the course of scientific research and in volunteer initiatives on the basis of a network of social assistance institutions partnering with the HEI; 3) the use of the Pearson criterion χ^2 in the statistical processing of experimental data in groups E_1 and K_1 , allowed to determine a significant difference in the readiness of future specialists of the control and experimental groups after the experiment and to prove the effectiveness of the experimental work.

A promising direction for further research is to identify opportunities to use the developed scientific and methodological support for training social professionals to form a healthy lifestyle of pupils in the system of further professional development of social sphere specialists and in training volunteers.

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REVIEW ARTICLE

Implementation of Interactive Teaching Methods in the Process of Developing Professional-Communicative Proficiency of Future Pilots

Authors' Contribution:

A – Study design;
B – Data collection;
C – Statistical analysis;
D – Data interpretation;
E – Manuscript preparation;
F – Literature search;
G – Funds collection

Kumpan O. O.^{1 ABDE}, **Kharlamova L. S.**^{2 DFG}¹ Flight Academy of National Aviation University, Ukraine**Received:** 28.08.2019; **Accepted:** 24.09.2019; **Published:** 30.11.2019**Background and Aim of Study:****Abstract**

The research deals with the methods of interactive teaching techniques implementation and their effectiveness assessment during professional language training of future pilots. These techniques are not only aimed to improve language proficiency, but ensure professional expertise and its implementation in the future professional activity. The aim of the study: to define professional language proficiency, to determine and describe interactive teaching methods able to facilitate in developing language skills that meet ICAO language proficiency requirements.

Material and Methods:

The systematic collection and analysis of all subjective and objective information necessary to define and validate defensible curriculum purposes that satisfy the language learning requirements of students within the context of particular institutions that influence the learning and teaching situation are made. Holistic descriptors and language proficiency assessment scale developed by ICAO are studied. Innovative teaching approaches and methods are studied and implemented. Interactive teaching techniques are implemented and the results are assessed during the training course on Aviation English.

Results:

Recent studies have proved that methods based on interaction considerably increase students' motivation, willingness to learn, improve and expedite language skills acquisition and facilitate in their successful implementation in real situations.

Conclusions:

The demands for language proficiency defined by ICAO are not limited by merely knowledge of a set of grammar rules, vocabulary and ways of pronouncing sounds. It is a complex interaction of that knowledge with a number of skills and abilities, which can be developed through interactive teaching methods.

Keywords:

language proficiency, interactive learning, interactive methods, role play, case study, brainstorming, multimedia learning.

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Introduction

Lack of plain language proficiency is often cited as a contributing factor in some accidents. While the focus of ICAO language proficiency requirements is on improved aeronautical radiotelephony communications, language also plays a role in cockpit resource management (CRM) and has been cited as a contributing factor in incidents/accidents where miscommunication happened within a flight crew. By meeting language proficiency requirements, flight crews, especially multi-national flight crews, will have the added safety benefit of better CRM (ICAO, 2010). Thus, acquisition of language proficiency for future pilots is considered to be one of the main targets of professional training. Here we should mention the main components of foreign language instruction goals: a) the acquisition of the knowledge of language skills for general communication use; b) exposing learners to other cultures and ideas; and c) fostering an appreciation of differences in cultures and ways of thinking. (Norris, 2006, p. 577). However, future pilots have specific and sometimes immediate language needs that require more than generalized or dispositional knowledge alone since their professional activity involves expertise in a specific area of communication. English for radiotelephony communications as well as Aviation English refer to what is called Language for Specific Purposes. Language for specific purposes (LSP) courses are those in which the methodology, the content, the objectives, the materials, the teaching, and the assessment practices all stem from specific, target language uses based on an identified set of specialized needs. Therefore, the content and focus of the language instruction is narrowed to a specific context or even a particular subset of tasks and skills. Importantly, the context and the people involved (e.g., learners, professionals in the field) drive LSP curriculum – unlike general purposes language instruction, which is often driven by theory alone (Widdowson, 1983). Moreover, in the scope of professional language training, we refer to the term “professional-communicative competence”, forming of which is a complicated, long and multifaceted process requiring students’ intensive engagement and interaction. Zimmjaja (2003) states that competence – is “an actual, formed personal quality as based on knowledge, intellectual and personally determined social-professional characteristics of an individual, his personal quality”.

In order to train a person able to interact within a certain professional sphere, professionalization of study curriculum is required. That means that professional component of education curriculum considers foreign language training as a social process of forming a professional oriented person with sufficient language proficiency. In addition, this describes the specifics of foreign language training curriculum for a specialist capable of information-communication activity in a particular sphere. Efficiency and quality of forming the future pilots’ professional-communicative competence depends on the level of consideration and realization of modern requirements in aviation community stated in Manual on the Implementation of ICAO Language Proficiency Requirements. A teacher’s role in the

language proficiency, that is an inherent part of a professional communication competence, acquisition should also be mentioned. The aim of professional training is to develop the essential CRM qualities, in particular, quick-thinking, decision making, leadership, reaction, attention, long- and short-term memory. Involving interactive teaching methods facilitate in achieving the most essential goals of training future pilots.

Interactive learning is defined as the process of exchanging and sharing of knowledge resources conducive to innovation between an innovator, its suppliers, and/or its clients. It may start with a resource-based argument, which is specified by introducing competing and complementary theoretical arguments, such as the complexity and structuring of innovative activities, and cross-sectorial technological dynamics. It is recognized as the practice of involving learners in the educational process by encouraging them to bring their own experience and knowledge into the process, while also contributing to defining or organizing their learning.

Interactive teaching styles are based on a simple principle: without practical application, students often fail to comprehend the depths of the study material. Interactive teaching is also beneficial for you as the teacher in a number of ways, including: a) measurable student accomplishments; b) flexibility in teaching; c) practice makes perfect; d) student motivation.

The aim of the study. To define professional language proficiency, to determine and describe interactive teaching methods able to facilitate in developing language skills that meet ICAO language proficiency requirements.

Materials and Methods

Interactive teaching methods were studied by national and foreign scientists: Alderson (2005); Angelo and Cross (1993); Bean (1996); Blake and DeVries (2004); Gonzalez (2015); Harwood (2010); Hayes (1989); Jolliffe (1991); Knapen (2018); Mayer (2005, 2009); McGlynn (2001); Melnyk (2017); Melnyk and Pypenko (2017, 2018); Morrison-Shetlar and Marwitz (2001); Nickolaeva and Sopova (2015); Pometun and Pirozhenko (2002, 2004); Reinders and White (2010); Silberman (1996); Trace, Hudson, and Brown (2015); VanGundy (2005); Veen, Lam, and Taconis (1998); Watkins (2005); Yee (2000), and others. ICAO adopted language proficiency requirements and published the ways of their implementation as well as principals of aviation specialists’ language training. The effectiveness of implementation of interactive teaching techniques is checked in the process of professional language training for future pilots and preparation aviation specialists for language proficiency testing according to the ICAO scale.

Results

Upon a thorough analysis of the interactive learning styles and techniques and estimated their effectiveness and propriety in the process of professional-communication competence and expertise of future pilots, the following activities have been implemented into the training process:

I. Role plays.

Role play is a technique that allows managing realistic situations and solving realistic problems that can emerge during professional activity through interaction with other people in a managed way with the aim to develop experience and test various strategies in a supported environment.

Depending on the goal of the activity, students can either play the roles they are likely to take possibly in their future professional activity or can play the opposite part in the conversation or interaction. Does not matter which part is taken, they are both effective in achieving significant learning and developing communication skills.

In the other words, role plays are used to allow students to practice speaking in a conversational situation, build confidence and fluency, assess progress, and put learning into action.

Here is the example how to use the technique in the process of teaching Aviation English at the Flight Academy: upon discussing the topic «Fire on board» and the division of duties among the crew, the students are offered to role-play the situation of fire on board whose aim is acquisition fluency, vocabulary and interaction. The cards with the description of a role and instructions, for example:

- The Firefighter (the first cabin crewmember that finds the fire): shall alert the cabin crewmembers, take the nearest appropriate fire extinguisher, immediately locate the source of the fire, extinguish the fire.

- The Communicator (the second cabin crewmember on the scene in charge of the communicating information about the fire) shall inform the flight crew of the following: fire location, fire source, severity/density of fire and/or smoke (color of smoke/odor), firefighting progress, number of fire extinguishers used.

- Cabin Crewmember No. 5 (directly involved in the firefighting effort) shall provide assistance, such as: relocating passengers, providing first-aid, calming and reassuring passengers.

- First Officer shall communicate with the cabin crew members, report the captain about the problem, communicate with ATC – declare the emergency, your position and intention to land at the nearest suitable aerodrome.

- Passenger No. 1 is terribly scared and do not want to follow the cabin crew member's instruction.

- Passenger No. 2 is in panic and screams that everyone will die, etc. are given to the students and upon the command "Fire!" they have to start playing their role. It is recommended to take a video, since it is rather problematic to assess student during the activity. The video can also be used for every student's performance analysis.

Despite some language errors, students' performance demonstrated deep involvement in the activity as well as sufficient knowledge on the topic. Moreover, being asked about the crew's duties and problems the passengers can cause in case of fire on board, the students did not have any difficulties in rendering the information.

II. Brainstorming.

According Cambridge Dictionary (2019) "to brainstorm (of a group of people)" means "to suggest a lot of ideas for a future activity very quickly before considering some of them more carefully".

Brainstorming, as a form of the student-centered learning approach, is the activity that facilitates to generate creative thoughts and ideas. The student-centered learning (Lea, Stephenson, & Troy, 2003) refers to a reflexive approach to the teaching and learning processes for both teacher and learners. SCL is considered to be a process that focuses on deep learning and understanding, since it encourages students to take an active role in the learning process. That is a process wherein a group attempts to find a solution for the specific problem by aggregating all the spontaneous opinions or suggestions given by each group member individually is called as brainstorming. By expressing own ideas and listening to the ideas others express, students make adjustments to their own knowledge or vision, accommodate new information and increase their levels of awareness. This method of teaching is based on the interaction between the teacher and the learner or between the learner and other learner, as this helps in the development of thinking methods.

The key objectives of the brainstorming are to: make students focused on a particular topic, generate and express as many ideas as possible, teach to accept and respect opinions that differ from their own, encourage learners to share their ideas and opinions, demonstrate to students' appreciation and acceptance of their knowledge and their language proficiency, provide students with an opportunity to share ideas and expand their existing knowledge by building on each other's contributions. This type of activity involves mastering the ability to give persuading arguments as well as to express agreement or disagreement, which considerably improves interaction between students.

Generally, the brainstorming is carried on in the following ways:

1. First of all, the group leader/facilitator outlines the problem requiring a decision. The problem is clearly stated such that the members can easily understand it and focus their direct attention on it.

2. Once the problem is defined, the participants are asked to share their opinions through which the problem can be tackled. Here the aim is to get as many ideas as possible; its feasibility is checked later.

3. The participants are required to give away their ideas freely without considering any financial, legal or organizational limitations.

4. The evaluation of ideas is done in the later stage. Therefore, any criticism, judgment, or comment is strictly prohibited during the brainstorming session, and the participants are told not to indulge in these.

The following brainstorming activity can be offered to students during Aviation English classes: Due to the fuel emergency, pilots have to make an emergency landing outside of the aerodrome. Students are given nine pictures of landing sites off the airfield such as a forest, a river, an ocean, ploughed land, a corn field, a motorway, a swamp, a valley surrounded by mountains, etc (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Landing sites for off-field landing.

Students have to rank them from the best one to the worst one, listing the advantages and disadvantages of the terrain types. Prior to commencing the activity, students are offered the expert's opinion concerning the emergency landing and choosing the landing site. Students' performance is assessed due to the following descriptors: fluency, structures, pronunciation, interaction and vocabulary. The willingness to defend own point of view makes students take active part in the discussion.

III. Case-study.

The method of case-study or specific situations is a method of active problem-situation analysis based on learning by addressing specific problems – situations. Particular cases (situations, stories, problems, in other word “case”) are used for common analysis, discussion or solving a problem that refers to a definite area of a learned discipline. Case study is applied in the students groups and can be divided into the following stages: the represented analysis of the situation, defining a problem, searching and collecting additional information (if required), discussing various options for solving the problem, choosing the most appropriate solution based on comparing all available options, presentation and defending the resolution.

During learning and comparing different plane types, their technical characteristics, capabilities, advantages and disadvantages, students have to make decision on the following: an airline wants to expand its fleet and is going to purchase five aircraft. The matter of the discussion is which type to choose: Boeing 737 or Airbus 320. The activity is conducted in the form of the Board of Directors meeting. The factors to be compared: the fly-by-wire concept (how much of human factor is involved), passenger capacity, fuel efficiency, cost and availability of maintenance, failures and crashes statistics. I would recommend setting time limits in

order to develop students' quick thinking, the ability required for pilots, as well as effective decision-making. While coming to a common decision students demonstrated flexibility and ability to adjust their point of view due to availability of new information.

IV. Multimedia learning.

Multimedia learning is the next innovative method. It is the combination of various media types as texts, images, pictures, audio and video materials using which the information is presented to the learners.

Multimedia learning is a cognitive theory of learning which has been popularized by the work of Mayer (2009) and others.

Mayer (2009, p. 223) identifies the following twelve multimedia instructional principles:

1. Coherence Principle – People learn better when extraneous words, pictures and sounds are excluded rather than included.
2. Signaling Principle – People learn better when cues that highlight the organization of the essential material are added.
3. Redundancy Principle – People learn better from graphics and narration than from graphics, narration and on-screen text.
4. Spatial Contiguity Principle – People learn better when corresponding words and pictures are presented near rather than far from each other on the page or screen.
5. Temporal Contiguity Principle – People learn better when corresponding words and pictures are presented simultaneously rather than successively.
6. Segmenting Principle – People learn better from a multimedia lesson is presented in user-paced segments rather than as a continuous unit.
7. Pre-training Principle – People learn better from a multimedia lesson when they know the names and characteristics of the main concepts.

8. Modality Principle – People learn better from graphics and narrations than from animation and on-screen text.
9. Multimedia Principle – People learn better from words and pictures than from words alone.
10. Personalization Principle – People learn better from multimedia lessons when words are in conversational style rather than formal style.
11. Voice Principle – People learn better when the narration in multimedia lessons is spoken in a friendly human voice rather than a machine voice.
12. Image Principle – People do not necessarily learn better from a multimedia lesson when the speaker's image is added to the screen.

Multimedia learning is effectively used during ESP classes and has proved to be the tool for not only acquiring language proficiency, but a professional competence as well. For instance, discussing aerodynamic movements of the plane it is essential to provide students with images to establish a link between the explanation and the movement itself. It enables them to learn deeper since additional navigation aids are provided (see Figure 2).

All above mentioned methods have been compiled in the study guide “Supplementary complex of interactive lessons on Aviation English” that is currently being practically evaluated during the future aviation specialists training.

Figure 2. Roll and the way it is controlled.

Discussion

The importance of interactive approach to teaching language as well as any professional knowledge and expertise acquisition cannot be overestimated. Owing to this fact, the issue has been discussed and researched for a long time. A great number of theories as well as practical implementation methods have been appeared.

Veen et al. (1998, pp. 31–39) state that the importance of interactivity lies in the fact that it provides learning dialogue, knowledge presenting structure flexibility and learning activity autonomy.

Yee (2000), the author of interactive techniques, considers interactive methods to be the most effective ones. They involve a collection of more than 100 teaching strategies that aim to engage students in studying process. Most of them encourage the natural acquisition of language, not learning. There is an important distinction between language acquisition and language learning. Children acquire language through a subconscious process during which they do not study grammatical rules. The same as they acquire their first language. Acquiring language, the learner needs a source of natural communication.

According to Blake and DeVries (2004), brainstorming activities that provide a meaningful learning environment in a relaxed atmosphere can be used as one of the strategies to promote speaking skills.

The cognitive theory of multimedia learning (CTML) centers on the idea that learners attempt to build meaningful connections between words and pictures and that they learn more deeply than they could have with

words or pictures alone (Mayer, 2009). According to CTML, one of the principle aims of multimedia instruction is to encourage the learner to build a coherent mental representation from the presented material. The learner's job is to make sense of the presented material as an active participant, ultimately constructing new knowledge.

Conclusions

Summarizing everything stated above, the following conclusions can be made: interactive teaching techniques are the powerful tool able to ensure reaching the main goal of learning-teaching process – language and professional skills acquisition. The students are encouraged to be active members of the class, thinking on their own, using their own brains, resulting in long-term memory retention. Not only the students' knowledge will improve, but their interest, strength, team spirit and freedom of expression will increase as well.

Interactive teaching means instructing the students in a way they are actively involved with their own learning process. There are different ways to create an involvement like this: a) teacher-student interaction; b) student-student interaction; c) the use of audio, visuals, video; d) hands-on demonstrations and exercises.

Currently, the research is being conducted as for the interactive methods of teaching advantage in the comparison with traditional teaching methods, where the students of Flight Academy of National Aviation University are involved.

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SOCIAL SCIENCES

Psychology

СОЦІАЛЬНІ НАУКИ

Психологія

OVERVIEW

Theoretical Preparation of Future Practical Psychologists in the Conditions of Modern Higher Education for the Applied Analysis of Behavior in primary school educational activity

Authors' Contribution:**Tantsura A.S.**^{1 BDFG}, **Funtikova O.O.**^{1 ABDG}

A – Study design;

B – Data collection;

C – Statistical analysis;

D – Data interpretation;

E – Manuscript preparation;

F – Literature search;

G – Funds collection

¹ Classical Private University, Ukraine**Received:** 22.10.2019; **Accepted:** 14.11.2019; **Published:** 30.11.2019**Background and
Aim of Study:****Abstract**

At present, there is a great need to define and substantiate the scientific provisions of a holistic system of training the future specialist for the applied analysis of student's behavior in primary school's educational activities. In our view, there are not enough theoretical and practical materials to prepare a future psychologist in elementary school.

The aim of the study: to substantiate the system of preparation of future practical psychologists for the applied analysis of behavior in primary school educational activity.

Material and Methods:

In the study, the following general scientific methods were used: analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalization.

Results:

Theoretical knowledge in the educational psychology and pedagogical disciplines not only influence the thinking of the future specialist to master a logically organized specific class of ideal objects of psychology, their properties, relationships and changes, but also enable the immanent unfolding of the content, as the starting point of the movement of thought in the practical point of motion.

Conclusions:

Requirements for the content of education of practical psychologists have been updated. Conceptual bases development of self-design of future practical psychologist's professional activity, creation and substantiation of his personality and definition of basic characteristics of his activity, development of self-realization of personality of psychologist's practice in professional activity will allow them to successfully carry out the process of preparation of specialist in applied analysis of problems of behavior of elementary school students.

Keywords:

age psychology, general psychology, basics of psychocorrection, pedagogical psychology, social psychology, psychodiagnostics, psychological service.

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Introduction

Preparation of the future specialist in higher education is the main goal of the state policy in the field of education, which provides the creation of conditions for the development of personality and professional self-realization, updating the content of education and organization of educational processes in accordance with the market economy principles, modern scientific and technological achievements (Fagan & Wise, 1994; Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2014; Virna, 2012). Topic for today is the fulfillment of the main task of higher education: professional training of the individual, formation of specialists with higher education, capability of creativity, making optimal decisions, having the skills of self-education, ability to coordinate their actions with the actions of other participants in their educational environment (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2011).

Training of the future specialist is carried out according to the relevant standards of higher education. The orientation of the future practical psychologist on his professional development, self-improvement and ensuring a high level of competitiveness in the educational services market is ensured by appropriate conditions in the preparation process (Thomas, 1999).

Scientists have their vision of an ideal model for training future specialists in content orientation and duration of training, given greater freedom of choice in mastering the specialty, changes in the space, levels and forms of training that will affect the innovative performance of the future specialist (Lozova & Trotsko, 2012). It is necessary to have a polymodal representation of any pedagogical experience, moving away from the outdated mainstream verbal training methods, to provide search for new and effective ways of representing professional and oriented knowledge and skills of the future specialist (Chepelieva, 1998; Smith, 2002).

The role of psychology and modern approaches of the psychologist's activity in the educational space was studied by Melnyk (2013); Melnyk, Prokopenko, and Stadnik (2015).

There is a great need to define and substantiate the scientific provisions of a holistic system of training the future specialist for the applied analysis of students' behavior in elementary school educational activities.

The aim of the study. To substantiate the system of preparation of future practical psychologists for the applied analysis of behavior in primary school educational activity.

Materials and Methods

Preparing a future specialist for applied behavioral analysis of elementary school, students should take into account the fundamental principles of behavior in school, the philosophy of positivism, reflection on the subject of influence in the content of positive behavioral changes in the subject and the behavior of the subject and behavior.

In the study, the following general scientific methods were used: analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalization.

Results and Discussion

For the preparation of the future practical psychologist the important role is played by the disciplines of the specialty and the disciplines of the professional direction in terms of content, training courses should be integrated to ensure systematic learning of disciplines, to avoid duplication of educational material, to strengthen cross-curricular links, and to improve the organization of the educational process and the introduction of new learning technologies (D'jachenko & Kandibovich, 1993; Dutkevych & Savytska, 2005).

The organization of psychological and social-pedagogical activities in addressing behavioral problems, leading a healthy lifestyle, and shaping a health culture among primary school pupils was explored by Melnyk (2008, 2017).

According to the analysis of literature, the preparation of the future practical psychologist is reflected in the educational and professional program, curriculum of all disciplines with a list of knowledge, skills of the future specialist, which are necessary for successful professional activity in general educational institutions, and is carried out on the basis of studying the social cycle, natural sciences, theoretical, practical and professional training (Kyrychuk, 2002).

Practical training tasks: deepening theoretical knowledge through practical training; developing skills of future practitioners in educational institutions, particularly in primary schools; formation of creative research approach to pedagogical activity in work with elementary school students.

The analysis of curriculum and the schedule of the educational process for the preparation of the future practical psychologist in institutions of higher pedagogical education reflects the cycle of humanitarian and socio-economic training (13 academic disciplines), the cycle of scientific and natural preparation (8 disciplines), the cycle of professional and practical training (25 courses), a cycle of the variant part of the training (24 courses).

According to the curriculum and the timetable of the educational process, practical training provides: introductory practice in the first year (2 semesters) of 54 hours (1 week) and diagnostic and psycho-correction in the fourth year (8 semesters) of 324 hours (6 weeks).

For the future specialists the complex qualification examination in psychology includes the courses (Figure 1).

The program of the course "Age Psychology" and the corresponding textbooks provide the solution of a number of tasks of highly qualified professional training specialists, in particular: mastering the system of knowledge about the patterns of mental development; equipping students with the knowledge of psychological patterns of personality development at different stages of ontogeny (Pavelkiv, 2011).

The analyzed program of the course "Age Psychology" also provides a close connection with the disciplines: general psychology, social psychology, history of psychology, the basics of psycho-counseling and psycho-correction, psychology of personality.

It should be noted that from the course “Age Psychology” future specialists will gain knowledge about the mental development of the child from birth to school age, master the terminology, guidance in the age periods of the mental development and the essence of age crisis of the student and ways of overcoming them in school; learn to distinguish between conscious and unconscious manifestations of the psychology of elementary school students; future specialists will get acquainted with the specifics of diagnostic and collection of work with children of different school age. Formation of relevant professionally oriented knowledge and skills of the future specialist was facilitated by the study of topics: “Psychological development of a young school-age child”, “Psychology of a “heavy child”, “Characteristics of the development of the psychic in ontogeny”.

In our view, for future practical psychologists, an in-depth study of the topic of the “Associationist Concept of Learning by Watson and Gazri” is important, which proves the thesis of establishing associative stimulus-reactive communication on the basis of reinforcing the behavior of the subject.

The analyzed training course “Age Psychology” reflects the training of the future psychologist on the main 10 topics; among them there is one topic of the seminar dedicated to the developmental problems of the school-

age child “Psychology of the teenager and high school student”, which makes 10% of theoretical material.

Unfortunately, much attention is paid to adolescent development, his or her social situation, communication, self-expression needs, and increased sexual identification among others.

In our view, there is not enough theoretical and practical materials to prepare a future psychologist to work in elementary school.

We have analyzed the program of the course “General Psychology” and textbooks, that direct students to acquire knowledge and ideas about the mental activity of the younger generation as a means of reflection and transformation of the world; to analyze functioning of psychic patterns; expanding outlook and professional horizon (Maksymenko & Soloviienko, 2000).

Students are introduced to the structural components of the human psychology. Future specialists have acquired the skills to explain the features of the course of mental processes, understand the functioning of mental states and manifestations of mental properties; at the level of self-control and self-observation of their own mental states and behaviors, they can describe their functioning. In the process of preparing future specialists in applied behavioral analysis, it is important to focus on the acquisition of knowledge on the following issues (Figure 2).

Figure 1. The courses for the complex qualification examination in Psychology for the future specialists.

Figure 2. The main issues for the acquisition of knowledge of future specialists in applied behavioral analysis.

It is found that in the preparation of future specialists, the ability to adhere to a certain methodological approach to psychological research and analysis of mental processes and personality of the child is formed; to be guided in different theories, critically analyze different approaches to the basic psychological categories, use the knowledge gained in practical activity; to determine the basic properties of the individual, psychological mechanisms for determining his behavior; to take into account the individuality, uniqueness, inner potential of self-creation of personality.

The analysis of the main topics in general psychology proves that in the topic “The main stages of the formation of psychology as a science. Basic Psychological Schools and Areas” it is useful for future practical psychologists to consider in detail precisely the 3rd stage of development of psychology: psychology as the science of behavior, which studies the external manifestations of mental activity – behavior.

In the course of “Educational Psychology” future specialists know about the subject, tasks and methods of pedagogical psychology, history of formation and development of pedagogical psychology, cross-curricular links and system of categories of pedagogical psychology.

The educational course “Educational Psychology” contains 10 topics, among which there is a seminar lesson on the theme: “The concept of learning and its psychological mechanisms: psychological characteristics of the learning process, psychological analysis of didactic principles of teaching; peculiarities of educational motivation; factors affecting the effectiveness of learning”, as well as a seminar session “Psychological features and general patterns of the learning process: the ratio of learning and learning processes, the structure of learning, psychological features of the process of learning skills and skills; indicators of learning ability”.

Future psychologists have formed knowledge about psychological models of teaching and classification of types of learning, innovative teaching technologies, types of modern learning: programmable, sign-contextual, modular; types of learning: rapid and slow rates of acquisition of material by elementary school students, criteria for success in primary school, factors for learning effectiveness and ways to activate the educational activity of elementary school students.

We believe that in order to qualitatively prepare future practical psychologists for applied analysis of primary school students' behavior, it is necessary to consider in more detail the topic “Forms of learning: respondent, operant, verbal”, as a process and result of acquiring individual experience and adapting to specific conditions of existence; making new connections between different situations, causing the subject to change behavior.

The course “Cognitive Psychology” forms students' knowledge of psycholinguistics and has interdisciplinary links with general psychology, social psychology, psychological personality, pedagogical psychology, age psychology, experimental psychology.

The purpose of teaching the discipline is to form students' perceptions of cognitive psychology laws, and the task is to help students gain profound knowledge of current issues in psycholinguistics; to develop skills and competences for conducting experimental research in it and to correctly use the results obtained in future professional activity.

In our opinion, for future practical psychologists who purposefully prepares themselves for applied analysis of elementary school students, it is necessary to become acquainted with the topic of cognitive psychology “The theory of language by Homskij and Miller and the critique of behaviorism”, to find out behavioral approaches to linguistic nouns of child by adult. It is useful for students to become acquainted with Homskij and Miller's arguments and to be able to express their professional position, to argue their views on the scientific dispute between Homskij and Miller (1965) and Skinner.

The training course “Social Psychology”, places in the minds of future psychologists the knowledge of basic concepts, principles, provisions of social psychology, forms the skills and practical and research activities in the social field (Bihun, 2011).

Future specialists will learn information about the essence, place, role of social psychology during their studies; system of scientific knowledge and its conceptual apparatus, learn methods of research of social and psychological phenomena; methods of verbal and non-verbal communication for successful interaction with elementary school students; methods and means of interpersonal interaction between teacher and elementary school students.

Future specialists, through mastering the tasks of the course of social psychology, have developed the ability to analyze intragroup and group relationships between students, practically oriented approaches to solving problems of socialization of students in the educational environment by means of social and psychological influence.

In the context of the training course “Social Psychology”, future practical psychologists need to study in depth the topic “Contemporary direction of development of foreign social psychology: Skinner's theory of operant learning”, which includes the provisions: human behavior is determined, predicted and controlled by the environment; Respondent behavior is a response to a familiar stimulus; operant behavior is determined and controlled by the result, which will then be obtained.

It has been found out that the curricula for the training of the future practical psychologist in different domestic educational institutions include the “Workshop on psycho diagnostics and correction in education”, the training course “Fundamentals of psycho-correction work”, “Psychological correction”, “Practicum on group “Basics of psychological counseling”, “Personal crisis counseling”, “Organization of training communication with children of all ages”, “Psychological assistance to children who have been abused”, “Emergency psychological assistance”. Computer Psycho diagnosis, Psychological Assistance in Crisis, Family Counseling,

and Psycho diagnostics reflect the experience of mass practice of psychologists in educational institutions. The mentioned training courses are aimed at solving specific psychological and pedagogical problems and carrying out activities in the following areas: systematic psychological examination of children and adolescents, their groups and collectives, learning and developing conditions with the help of diagnostic tools. In conducting psychological diagnostics, a future psychologist to study pedagogical behavior problems of a primary school student determines the subject of psycho diagnostics – ways and means of measuring quantitative and qualitative specifics of behavioral responses in their dynamics; systemic relationships and causal relationships between the student's behavior and his or her surroundings; a diagnostically relevant object of psycho diagnostics, as the conformity of professional knowledge to the ways of studying pedagogical problems of the student's behavior in the educational process and the opportunity to carry out applied analysis.

Psycho diagnostics is the basis of direct practical diagnostic work of a psychologist on the basis of theoretical and methodological and concrete-methodical principles of using psycho diagnostic tools and forming a psycho diagnostic conclusion about the state of the measured psychological variable; methods and techniques of diagnostics of the most versatile psycho diagnostic objects (personality traits, abilities, motives, consciousness and consciousness, etc.); differential psychometrics as a mathematical methodology for measuring individual differences in people (Panok, 2002).

Conclusions

1. At present, there is a great need to define and substantiate the scientific provisions of a holistic system of training the future specialist for applied analysis of students' behavior in primary school educational activities. In our view, there is not enough theoretical and practical material to prepare a future psychologist to work with elementary school students.

2. We believe that theoretical knowledge in the educational psychology and pedagogical disciplines not only direct the thinking of the future specialist to master a logically organized specific class of ideal objects of psychology, their properties, relationships and changes, but also enable the immanent unfolding of content, is the starting point of the thoughts of the future practical psychologist.

3. Requirements for the content of education of practical psychologists have been updated. Conceptual bases development of self-design of future practical psychologist's professional activity, creation and substantiation of his personality and definition of basic characteristics of his activity, development of self-realization of personality of psychologist's practice in professional activity will allow them to successfully carry out the process of preparation of specialist in applied analysis of problems of behavior of elementary school students.

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BRIEF REPORT

Phenomenological Perspective in Researching Immigrant Children's Experience

Authors' Contribution:Batuchina A.^{1 ABDF}, Straksiene G.^{1 EFG}

A – Study design;

B – Data collection;

C – Statistical analysis;

D – Data interpretation;

E – Manuscript preparation;

F – Literature search;

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¹ Klaipeda University, Lithuania**Received:** 29.10.2019; **Accepted:** 20.11.2019; **Published:** 30.11.2019**Background and
Aim of Study:****Abstract**

Migration is a complicated and complex social phenomenon. Arriving in a new country, immigrants find themselves in a strange, unfamiliar environment; simultaneously they may have left behind almost everything that they had in their home country. Such a life event changes the relationship between a person and their things: immigrants lose their connection with the things left behind, while new connections with the things of the host country have yet to be forged. This is a natural process of an adult's migration. But what is it like for a child?

The aim of the study: to reflect the experiences of immigrant children and their changing relationship with things in phenomenological methodology approach.

Material and Methods:

The article is based on hermeneutic phenomenology, when children migrating is analysed as a phenomenon. In order to investigate such phenomena phenomenology as a research strategy is applied. Its data were collected using several methods. The main method was the unstructured phenomenological interview with children and adults who due to economic reasons left their home country and came to live in another while being children together with their parents (or one of them). Having changed the country, they had also to change schools.

Results:

Show the uniqueness of the children migration experience and reflects it in the phenomenological matter.

Conclusions:

Children migration experience is often underestimated from the position of grown-ups, while children view migration differently, as they see things, objects and space around them differently (they see, feel and imagine world in a totally unique manner). That is why children taken out of their usual and normal lifestyle, home space facing totally different world, with strange and unfamiliar things, facing the world of unpredictability, temporality and eternity, fantasy and dreams, where misunderstood, or unnoticed are left alone, even while being surrounded by people.

Keywords:

migration, phenomenology, children, qualitative research, things.

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Introduction

Why should child migration be analyzed phenomenologically? There will be no surprise if I say that migration itself is a very complicated life event for a person: you have to leave your country, your friends, even your culture, everything you know, and then move yourself and belongings to a place which is strange and alien. For grown-ups, such a move might be decided by the promise of improved living conditions, economic and social benefits. But for a child, such decisions are often made without them, or without an understanding of such adult concerns. At the same time children experiences of migration, perhaps due to their status as dependents, may be underestimated, and thus they may be left alone with it. Grynberg's (2012) dissertation, *Disjunctions and Contradictions: An Exploration of My Childhood Migration Experience through Visual Art*, provides a powerful example of how some may the minimize the meaning of migration for a child.

All around us is the tinkle of china and the reassuring murmur of people politely conversing. I turn around to look at the man I've been seated next to at this conference dinner. We acknowledge each other with a smile, and anxiously wonder how to begin the conversation.

"Hello, my name is Jonathan."

"Pleased to meet you, I'm Carmella, I respond."

I watch as his eyes register this information: "That's an unusual name. Are you from an Italian background?"

"No, actually Carmella is also an Israeli name, I was born there."

A small frown now appears between his eyes as his gaze moves somewhat furtively over my hair, clothes and jewelry.

"Really! I never would have picked you as a migrant, you don't even have a hint of a foreign accent."

I smile, and think that he is too polite to add, "and you don't look like you come from anywhere else."

I decide to offer some more information: "Well, I arrived in Melbourne when I was eight years old."

"Oh," he sighs, the furrows between his eyes softening, "then you are not a real migrant, you were just a child." (Grynberg, 2012, p. 1).

Jonathan discounts Carmella's migrant experience as less than real, since she was but a child when she moved. So while the adult experience of migration may be recognized as an event of significance and thus worthy of attention, the uniqueness of the same event for a child may be overlooked. Indeed, despite the abundance of research on migration, child migration has been given little analysis from a pedagogical perspective. Where it has been investigated, some researchers have turned to hermeneutic phenomenology to provide insight to this often memorable event for a child. Topics have included: longing for home (Winning, 1990), speaking of home (Winning, 1991), physical self-awareness of a child-migrant (Kirova & Emme, 2008), the child's perception of home when away from home (Dachyshyn, 2013), the experience of studying in a foreign language (Lee, 2005), and what home is when we have left it (Norris, 1990).

The aim of the study. To reflect the experiences of immigrant children and their changing relationship with things in phenomenological methodology approach.

Materials and Methods

For the current study, data were collected using several methods. The main method was the unstructured phenomenological interview with 17 children and adults who have or used to have the experience as a child of leaving their home country and coming to live in another one together with their parents (or care-givers, however in this research there were no such participants) legally and voluntarily. Changing of a country means that they had also to change schools. Various additional data on children's migrating were collected from the published material including autobiographies, publicly available online sources, essays written specially for the current investigation, and phenomenological literature. The article presents only a small part of the research results; they reflect the migrant child's experiences when facing new things in a new country and a school upon arrival at a new country. The data were analyzed following van Manen's (2014) recommendations. The data collection focused on concrete lived experience descriptions of migrant children, referring to which the anecdotes were written, in order to recreate the lived experiences of migrant children, but now in a "transcended form" (van Manen, 2014, p. 250).

Results and Discussion

Things and Migration

A person is closely related to the things that surround him or her. Merleau-Ponty (2004) shows that people are honeyed together with things. Such bonding denotes the relationship between the object and us and reveals that we are surrounded by things or forced to treat and see them only in a certain way. A thing has a certain peculiarity to allure, to attract, or to stimulate interest of those standing before it. The things of our world are not simply neutral objects that are in front of us or that are designed to fill our field of vision. Each of them symbolizes or imposes a certain way of being or doing, and provoking reactions that may be positive, negative, or otherwise. People's tastes, lifestyle, attitudes, and the world are reflected in the things that are chosen to surround him.

Our relationship with things is not distant: each thing affects our bodies and the way we live (Merleau-Ponty, 2004). As van den Berg (1972, p. 32) declares, "who wants to become acquainted with man, should listen to the language spoken by the things in his experience". In other words, a person does not live on an empty planet, but is always around things, and these things show up differently depending on who that person is, where he lives, what he likes and prefers. Heidegger also presents the idea of the significance of a thing in human's life. According to Heidegger (1971), "being human is dwelling, that is, staying with and among things" (p. 157). The life of a human being is not possible without things. Following this idea, a human is always surrounded by things that create his or her life or things are "chosen" according to one's life.

In the context of migration, and especially in the context of child migration, things can have a particular significance. The significance of things becomes especially relevant in the moments of departure from the native country and arrival at a new country. Things that are important to a child may be left when they are leaving the home country. Maybe the child had certain memories related to them or they might have also created his or her routine and daily life. They were used by the child, had lain nearby, were constantly available and therefore were taken for granted, such things could be a favorite book from the library to read before bed, old sneakers to play on the wet grass, a tree house to hide from the parents, even an old bench in the backyard, where the first cigarette was tried. All these things were always nearby and always “available”. When leaving the home country, things, their shape, volume, functionality, and even the human relationship with them receive a different meaning. Things and everything that is associated with them are again evaluated by the child; they are no longer taken for granted: the book is left at the hometown library – there is nothing to read before bed, old sneakers are thrown away – you cannot play on the wet grass with the new ones, the tree house is sold together with the house, where the bench is placed. All these things are left at the home country, and only a few are taken with me and I need to decide which ones.

Leaving a country people ask themselves: will I need or use this thing? What does it mean to me? Does it bring me important memories? In the reflections person “touches” each thing – asking himself whether he or she will be able to or should take it with him or her or not. And if one thing has material value (if its price is high – it cannot be left; if it is convenient and necessary – it will be useful in a new country), others have emotional value – remind of the connection with people who are left in the homeland; such case is described in the anecdote provided below:

In one box I have two little glass angels and two walnuts, sprayed with silver paint. I received them from my aunt and cousin for Christmas, and I have been putting them at a visible spot. I really can’t leave them, so I want to take them with me. I have a little sun drawn by my stepfather. When I was a teenager, I came up with a nickname for myself: “Little Sun”. He and my mother always knew how to make fun of me and when it was my birthday, he drew a little sun on a small piece of paper – but it’s me, really. He drew an upturned nose, this dimple on the chin; he drew big thick eyebrows, protruding ears. That’s me. I will never throw it away (Agne).

Agne tells about some things, some bagatelles that she has brought from her home country. For many, these things may appear with no value; but to her, who has left not only her home country but also her friends and relatives; these things have meaning provided by memories and relations with the left ones. Each thing has its own story and is related to a certain event in her life moment. A child sees in those things not a bunch of rubbish, she sees memories, faces of her friends, and she sees her old life in them: she is examining the things one by one, and she is making decisions on each piece, like

selecting and choosing memories from her home country to take with her. And those memories are put in a thing, which she is able to carry with her through out her journey to the new country, the country, with no old friends, no relatives and no memories, she used to have. Meanwhile, the things that are left behind and cannot be taken away may be still in connection with the child even after one’s departure. On the one hand, the things left behind become alienated; they are considered no longer belonging to the person. However, such alienation occurs not immediately, or may not appear at all. The left things still have an intimate connection that does not disappear in one day or just after leaving the things: my former house, my bed, my wardrobe and my desk. The thing is called “My” even if it no longer officially belongs to me, but may belong to another person now. From my own perspective, I spent my childhood and teenage years in an apartment uptown, and even though it is already 15 years since I have lived there, every time I have a chance to drive through that neighbourhood, I am trying to see how my old room’s window looks like, repeating in my head “my room”. A similar connection between a thing and a child can be seen in the following anecdote. Roma, a migrant girl shared how much she misses her bed, thus, revealing how important this left thing was to her.

Most of all I miss my bed. I have a new bed in my new country, but I can’t sleep in it. I can’t sleep deeply: when you close your eyes and it’s already morning. In my bed I always slept like this, I knew how to. Now I don’t (Roma).

Roma describes the connection between her, as a human, and a bed, as a thing. While living in another country and using other things she remembers how important the things are that were left in her homeland. In other words, the left thing no longer belongs to a child but the connection with it remains even after losing it. Heidegger (1971) pointed out aptly that a person may appreciate home (the home world) more when he or she loses it: perhaps then he or she becomes fully aware of what home is and means in his or her life. A child who has just lost or intends to lose things reflects on their meaning, and in such a way discovers them anew and the thing is no longer taken for granted.

All in all, upon arrival at another country, new things may yet have a different meaning. New things may be inevitably “discovered” in a new country in the course of migration. They force us to reconsider our place in the new space and to recall memories; they make us nostalgic, fearful, or even remorseful. Things become symbols that show the former life and future opportunities and reflect the current emotional and existential state. In this context, a question arises – how a migrant child experiences things when he or she has just arrived at the new country?

Things without Connection: Strangeness

Having left one’s native country, in a new country, the migrant child may face new things. These things have to replace the usual (old) things in their purpose and function. The first encounter with some new things may make a child feel confused or even uncomfortable. However, the question is what does a child experience when acquainting with new things in a new country? In

the anecdote provided below a migrant girl describes her surprise on the first day at school. She seems surprised by the seen things.

Everything is so strange, the doors of the rooms are with windows, so everyone could look at our class, the tables are round and they are standing in the middle of the class, not facing the board. In my school we have desks for two. The teacher stands in front and turns to the desks. When I went to my first English class I was amused, in an English classroom there were three old posters of the Harry Potter movie, while in a French class the poster from the book *Les Misérables*, the face of a girl. In Spanish, there were posters of a cat Garfield and a picture of a Buddha. When I saw all this I've lost my voice, I could not speak. I was staring at this poster during the entire lecture. I was panicking (Darja).

Darja tells how surprising she finds the arrangement of things in the school. Surrounded by new things she feels unusual. Their arrangement and even their presence in a school classroom are not acceptable and strange to her. What lies behind the strangeness of the things? How does a child experience that strangeness of things? Maybe a child sees strangeness as something unknown? Or something that might appear as unusual, since have never been seen? Let's look at the etiological meanings of the word strange.

The English word strange (adj.) means "from elsewhere, foreign, unknown, and unfamiliar". Clear relation can be seen with the term alien which has similar meanings – strange, foreign; an alien, stranger, foreigner. Another term that has a similar meaning is unusual, which is composed of a negative particle un and the verb use, and embraces such meanings as use, custom, practice, employment, skill, and habit. If something is unusual, we cannot or we do not know how to use it at first. At the same time, if something is strange it is usually not mine, and as a result, when we talk about something what is strange it is important to consider the meaning of the word own (mine, our, yours), since what is not mine, what does not belong to me, might be someone else's, stranger's. Analyzing the word own etymologically, it is clear that it is associated with the words to possess, have; rule, be in command of; have authority over. Of these synonyms it is seen that a thing to which we are accustomed to is as if under our control, we own it and use it. In other words, when we say, it is mine (my house, my pen, my school), we mean some certain personal relation with this object: this is a house I grew up in, or this is the pen I bought today, or this is a school I went to; the purpose, use, function, and occupied place of these things – all are familiar to us. Whereas things which we are not accustomed to are strange, foreign, unknown, and with no connection, since we have nothing in common with these things.

In migration terms strange and own actualize and their meanings become especially prevalent. Everything what is associated with the homeland is familiar, while new things of the immigration country become strange. Upon arrival in a new country, the old thinking – usual things and the awareness of their purpose, location and the need to use them – distorts; a child does not know what to do with things (how to behave with them) in a new world, what place in this world a certain thing occupies, what

is its purpose, peculiarity. Even though a child sees usual things: a table, chairs, a desk, all the things which were in his or her home country, but the child does not see himself or herself in, among or using these things. The child does not understand his or her relation with the thing.

A similar point is represented in Schutz's (1945) work "The Stranger". The author states that the discovery that things in the strangers' new surroundings look quite different from what he or she expected them to be at home is frequently the first shock to the stranger's confidence in the validity of his or her habitual "thinking as usual" (Schutz, 1945, p. 501). Interpreting this Schutz's theme of "thinking as usual" within the materialistic meaning, it can be seen that a migrant person finds himself or herself near things that he or she does not know, they seem strange, alien, not "my own": the usual perception of the world seems broken, and the vision of the new world is yet vague and unclear. Such word perception might be similar for children. As Langeveld (1984, p. 216) writes "the child lives in a world which provides him or her with a ready-made structure of qualities that offers security". He also says (Langevel, 1984, p. 220): "child's recognition of the world and her knowledge of the world are largely dependent on the help or influence of others". It means if a child raised in a world of things (in the contexts of migration, world means home country), which he or she knew (learning from his or her birth and in the following life), appears in a new ready-made world of things, but which he or she knows nothing of and has problems acquainting with it, especially without other people around, the child loses his or her security, the child remains helpless. If a grown up person, due to his or her longer and richer life experience, might foreknow what one or another thing has in it, a child needs help to restore his or her "thinking as usual" state. Meanwhile, upon arrival in a new country, the child's "thinking as usual" is broken, since his or her perception of the world still relies on his or her native country and the country's values, while the new world is somewhat unknown to him or her, therefore, seemingly unpredictable.

In a collection of poems "No Return Address: A Collection of Poems", Waters (2015) dwells on migration experiences. In "No return address", the author is grateful for the memories of his former life, for the world before emigration, which he had, which was known to him, and which was predictable:

"Bob, I am grateful for your

Three letter name.

It's another reminder of home

Of a world predictable

Of a life I had".

The former world is presented as predictable, and its things are known, they remind of home where a person can feel like in a homeland. Meanwhile, the world of migration is unpredictable: unknown things do not allow predicting what will happen, and therefore, things may force the person to be always prepared or even fearful. For children, when seeing unusual things that do not meet the perception of their world, they cannot predict and foresee what their life will be in a new country, in a new school. The vision for the future, which is based on

conventional thinking of the native country, does not match the seen things and their position, their need or function in the new country, and restoration of such vision requires effort and even help of the others.

Things without Connection: Temporality

New things however, do not immediately become one's own. As it is described above, new things are strange, can be intimidating because of their unpredictability or may force to imagine a different life, which will be in a new country, and/or force to be aware of where he or she is, as describe in the following anecdote:

Our new house is an old building with several floors. The flooring on the second floor is unstable, squeaking. We go to the toilet or shower on the second floor in groups so it isn't so scary because we have someone to hold hands. All children slept in one room, the small children slept in one bed, the older on the floor. The house seemed so dark, like those haunted houses in movies. We can't get used to it. It seemed to me like a ghost (Gabriele).

Gabriele was 11 years old when her family and she moved to another country. She describes her memories about the first family house in the new country; the memories of that house are very vague, as if through a mist. Her recollection is of an old, unstable structure: it seems that the house could have collapsed at any time. The family lived there for more than 2 years, quite a long time to get used to this place and get familiar with it. But for Gabriele, this new house never became a home, for all that time the girl had imagined it as a temporal shelter – a place where she is just sleeping over for a few nights before some permanent place is going to be found. But what is really behind that temporality? By the term temporality I mean state of being for the short or long period of time and this period has a certain moment of ending, while something that lasts forever or always does not have an ending, speaking without any philosophical reasoning.

From the theoretical point of view migration can be defined as three types: short-term, long-term and circular immigration (Europos Migracijos Tinklas, 2010). The short-term immigration is defined as the migration with a particular motive or purpose (work, study, family reunion, etc.), after which people return to the country of origin or move further to another country (Europos Migracijos Tinklas, 2010). Meanwhile, long-term (permanent) migration is migration with the goal to stay permanently in the target country. Circular migration in general can be understood as a cycle of migration which is comprised of a migrant person's departure from his or her country of origin, stay for some time in another country, return to his or her country of origin and repeated departure to a foreign country (Europos Migracijos Tinklas, 2010). Long-term and circular migrations are different from short-term migration in the length of the period of departure. However, from the phenomenological point of view, each migration, regardless of its purpose and the planned time of departure, especially at the beginning of migration stage, might be seen as temporal, in other words, a person might feel that this period of migration might end one day and he or she will go back home. Such temporality lies within the feelings of the human

being, his or her seen environment and surrounding things.

In terms of things, as van Manen (2014, p. 306–307) writes, “materiality may guide our reflection to ask how things are experienced. The things are our world in its material thing like reality.” Thus, things are a world that reflects our vision and point of view we might say our inner state. To the contrary, a relation with the things may depend on our point of views and experiences. Gabriele felt that the house she and her family stayed in was not inhabited, there were none of the girl's things, no scent of a family, and no common home intimacy. She felt that she would not live in this house for the whole time, even though that was the first plan. In his essay on the “Hotel Room”, van Lennep (1987) describes how much intimate relations are in one or another person's home. Things, walls, the whole house is filled with the scent, feelings, emotions that reflect the life of a person living there. Van Lennep (1987) writes: We always enter someone's living room for the first time with a certain hesitation or embarrassment, that is into the room he “inhabits,” not because this room is an expression of himself, but because this dwelling refers to a much more intimate relation than any expression by him could ever be (p. 210).

Like to a guest, to another person who gets into a new place, this place, even if it is called one's own (mine), has so “little” in itself (p. 212) of what can be called one's own (my) room. No human being belongs here: it does not have his or her scent, nor chosen things. This relation with the house shows the girl's relation with her migration. She sees herself as a temporal guest in the new world of the new country. She does not recognize herself in this world, since there is no relation with this country. A new house, new things in this house are the symbols of her being new in this country.

Meanwhile, van Lennep (1987) writes that even a tourist coming to a new city and living in a hotel room after a long day spent in the city comes back to the room to rest and calls it “my room”. As the author writes, the pronoun “my” in the expression “my room” does not express my possession of it, but precisely a relation between me and the room. On the very first moment a person enters a new room, he or she begins “the process of inhabiting the room” (p. 212). And after some time in the course of inhabiting “the relation of intimacy has been created between this room and me” (p. 212). Van Lennep (1987) writes about experiences of grown-up people who, after a certain period of time in a new place, assume control over things, they become dependent on him or her, and in this way become more and more “his” or “hers”. And maybe with time such “dependency” replaces a sense of temporality, and an immigrant becomes more and more integrated into the new life.

The Imagined Value of Things

New things may bring the opposite feelings, create the illusion of a better life, and a vision for the future that soon may appear to be incorrect. Such a situation is described in an anecdote from Grynberg's (2012) dissertation:

My father and uncle were waiting for us at Essendon airport. My uncle drove us to the flat my father had rented for us. It was on the ground floor located in a

large building which faced St Kilda Road, a wide, leafy boulevard leading into the central business district of Melbourne. The block of flats consisted of three floors and had a number of exterior art decor features, such as faceted forms of decoration around its entrances and rounded corners on the upper storey verandas. It represented a stark contrast to the rectangular unadorned building which had been my home in Israel. When I entered the flat for the first time my interest centred around a black telephone which sat on a little ledge in the hallway. Although the telephone was not connected, I was overwhelmed by the idea that we were in possession of such an instrument which, until then, I had rarely seen in a private home. Its presence signified to me that Australia was a place of untold possible luxury. The reality of our life in Melbourne, however, proved to be somewhat different (Grynberg, 2012, pp. 24-25).

Children tend to imagine. Our imagination allows our mind to create a new image in the head. Imagination helps us to create, work, think, even feel, smell and taste things without these things being in front of us. There will be nothing surprising if I say that imagination is an important ability of our mind. Also, children use their imagination differently from grown-ups: they imagine, dream even create fantasies in their head more often. As Welsh (2013, p. 18) writes: "in dreaming children do not assume that the dream in contrast to waking reality is not real. They haven't yet learned to assume that their intimate experiences are "unreal" whereas the extended matter is "real". As a result, children create views in their head they start to believe in. Consequently, things, which were previously not seen very often and are the symbols of prosperity in the home country, in a child's mind move him or her into a richer world. Children, in comparison to grown-ups, have not yet learned to distinguish between a hidden meaning, direct meaning. Children are straight forward. If he or she sees a phone or other things, which he or she believes is a symbol of wealth, it means for a child that he or she is rich, even if the reality is proving different. The phone symbolises future life, which is better, richer and, perhaps, happier. As Merleau-Ponty (2005, p. 413) suggests, "The perception of other people and the intersubjective world is problematic only for adults. The child lives in a world which he unhesitatingly believes accessible to all around him... he subjects neither his thoughts, in which he believes as they present themselves, to any sort of criticism. He has no knowledge of points of view. For him men are empty heads turned towards one single, self-evident world where everything takes place, even dreams, which are, he thinks, in his room, and even thinking, since it is not distinct from words." Upon arrival at a new country and seeing new things, migrant children can create images of a better life in the future. This is especially true if the things and their "value" are very different from the life in the home country. Thus, migration as the end of problems, hardships or other challenges of the old life (associated with the finances received) is associated with "different" things. However things might bring not only projections of a better life, but also force a child to get lost in his or her own mind:

The first stop after our flight was in Stockholm and it took about one hour. My younger brother as usual had to visit one place. He does this everywhere he sees the toilet sign. I watched him and directed him to the right door with my eyes. However, just after 20 seconds, he ran out of the toilet as if he was scolded. He began to mumble nervously: "There are so many things hanging around, I don't know how to use them". I stood up and I went with him. I was used to Soviet toilets, so there's no surprise to me.

At first I thought that we went through the wrong door, and instead got into the plumbing museum of the twenty-first century. How? The walls were not drawn? On the floor there were no litter lying around? Seats were attached to the toilets, and next to them. Oh, my God! – Toilet paper. Shock therapy began there, where we had least expected it. (Michail)

Michail has lived his entire childhood and a great part of adolescence in the country which is radically different from the country to which he has emigrated. The boy and his family moved to the United States from the Soviet Union who had just collapsed. The new space that Michail saw unexpectedly stunned him by its distinctiveness, because it was very different from the space in his native country.

Michail leaves one country and comes to another, while each country is not only a political structure with geographical boundaries and its own history and traditions, but also a distinctive world, with a specific space, peculiar rules, and a way of life, and also specific things. These new things are the signs of the new world, showing that transition was made. A child without knowing these new signs is comparing with what he knew from the world he used to live in. The values he had through his short life are vanishing, replaced by the new cultural specifics. What is seen in the Michail's lived experience that a child starts to question why the surrounding which he expected to be absolutely inconspicuous brought amazement and misunderstandings in his own head the same time. He thought that a toilet without toilet paper, with painted in graffiti walls, and broken taps are normal and an ordinary thing, whereas an opposite situation, when toilets are clean and not broken, is a unique and even unreal. The things he saw blew up his old thinking, and understandings, and living standards he had, turned over his understanding of what is normal and abnormal, what is good and what is bad, forcing him to remember that he is really migrating.

Conclusions

The child moving from one country to another leaves his or her familiar world, and finds him or herself in a strange new world. The boundaries between these worlds are only partially drawn by the state border. Evidence of a different world lies in each new thing encountered, as a result every new thing is not taken for granted anymore. Thus, a child starts to question every new thing he or she sees, as he or she starts to question every meaning this thing brings. Those things become that new world the child has entered. Someone might say: "but this is the same for adults. Adults also question everything that they don't know". But we should not

forget how dependent children are and how complicated and unknown the new world appears to them. Same time children migration experience is often underestimated from the position of grown-ups, while children view migration differently, as they see things, objects and space around them differently. They do question world around them, while do not take it for granted, they see, feel and imagine world in a totally unique manner. That is why children taken out of their usual and normal lifestyle, home space facing totally different world, with strange and unfamiliar things, facing the world of unpredictability, temporality and eternity, fantasy and dreams, where misunderstood, or unnoticed are left alone, even while being surrounded by people.

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НАУКИ ПРО ЖИТТЯ
Науки про здоров'я

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Social Identification's Role for Work and Family Life Balance

Author's Contribution:

- A – Study design;
- B – Data collection;
- C – Statistical analysis;
- D – Data interpretation;
- E – Manuscript preparation;
- F – Literature search;
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Background and Aim of Study:**Abstract**

The research work considers whether workplace stress had a negative association with university teacher's family functioning, and if a social identification might a moderator role for this relationship.

The aim of the study: to define the social identification's role for work and family life balance.

Material and Methods:

The data were collected from participants (university teachers) with the scales (Perceived Stress Scale; Brief Family Relationship scale and The Three-Dimensional Strength of Group Identification scale) of multiple – choice questionnaire. Moderation analysis was conducted by using multiple linear regression analysis.

Results:

Author concludes that the impact of workplace stress on family functioning is dependent on individual's social identification level with their family group. It is because the bivariate analysis results showed that workplace stress was a negatively affected to the family functioning ($p < 0.05$). Moderation analysis indicated that the impact of workplace stress on family functioning is dependent on individual's social identity level with their family members. The interaction between social identification and workplace stress was significant ($p < 0.05$), that means social identification moderated the relationship between workplace stress and family functioning. Workplace stress would not negatively effect on family functioning ($p > 0.05$) that individual's whose social identification with their family was high. In contrast, lower identification with family had more significant negative impact from workplace stress on their family functioning.

Conclusions:

Social identification plays a significant effect for individual's work and family life balance. Individual's high social identification with their family is an effective coping method with workplace stress and, moderates the relationship between workplace stress and family functioning.

Keywords:

workplace stress, family functioning, coping, social identification.

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Introduction

Although there are studies have found several methods for dealing with workplace stress, finding effective coping methods with faculty member's workplace stress that impacted on their family functioning has still stayed a significant question. 'Coping' has been described by Lazarus & Folkman (1984) as 'thoughts and acts that people use to manage specific external or internal demands of stressors'.

The theoretical analysis has shown that social identification is a significant variable coping with workplace stress. According to research in the social-psychological platform, social identification is 'central to people's experiences of and reactions to, social and environmental stressors' (Haslam, O'Brien, Jetten, Volmedal, & Penna, 2005). 'Social identification' has been defined by Taifel (1978), 'an individual's self-concept which derives from his knowledge of his membership'. Considering this, Ellemers, Koetekaas, and Ouwerkerl (1999) study social identification divided into three components, a cognitive component, an evaluative component and an emotional component. These components have significant effect on members' social perception, feeling and behaviours (Taifel & Turner, 1979) which is based on individual's workplace stress on family functioning.

In addition, Avanzi et al. study (2018) with samples Swiss teachers found that strongly identified teachers receive more support from other members of group, and consequently lead them lower job burnout which is develops from workplace stress. Similarly, Zellars and Perrewe (2001) study examining influence of affective personality to emotional social support and job burnout suggested that individuals who engage conversations that focus on positive aspects of job report less burnout. It is because, interactions with a positive content is a significantly related to individual's job burnout (workplace stress) decrease, thoughts and feelings that linked with increased perceptions of personal self (Zellars & Perrewe, 2001) which play role for individual's relationship with their family.

The issues of prevention of mental disorders and their impact on the mental health of the individual were studied by Melnyk and Stadnik (2018).

Various aspects of training of future specialists in higher education were studied by Melnyk and Pipenko (2018). Specifically, family social identity's role discovered Baider, Ever-Hadani, Goldzweig, Wygoda, and Peretz (2003) study, and had shown that individual's stress buffering is directly related to their family, more specifically family support which is based on family member's social identification level. They identify couples who were experiencing high psychological distress reported lower levels of perceived family support than the normal levels of stress. This concept is confirmed by findings reported by Billings and Moos (1982) study, and authors concluded that work related stress on family relationship is directly associated with individual's family support. Despite men work stressors having greater impact, supportive social resources, such as family support provided more reduction for the effects of workplace stress on family functioning.

In addition, Kiecolt-Glaser et al. (1993) study, by

examining couple's production of stress hormones and low family relationships, found that women produced two particular stress hormones such as cortisol and norepinephrine during the discussion. Moreover, Kiecolt-Glaser et al. (1993) research indicated that couples with satisfying family relationship tended not to infections catch, and they confirm the findings by Beck (1984) that only a positive family interaction may reduce individual's stress, but relationships that involve a negative norms contribute stress (Kiecolt-Glaser et al., 1993).

Considering suggestions, social identification and its role for buffering individual's workplace stress is clear, in the present study there is the first attempt to research social identification as a moderator for decreasing workplace stress's negative impact on family functioning with samples in Kazakhstan. In addition, Wang, Repetti, and Campos (2011) found a relation between job stress and family social behavior and concluded that workplace stress affects family functioning in terms of talking and display of negative emotions. There was a significant correlation between these factors ($r=0.30$, $p<0.05$). The current study there takes account of these correlation coefficients, and proposes that if workplace stress affects family functioning, social identification would be a significant predictor moderating the relationship between workplace stress and family functioning of Kazakhstan teachers.

Thus, the main hypotheses formulated as following:

H. 1. Workplace stress would be negatively associated with family functioning.

H. 2. Social identification would be a moderator in a relationship between workplace stress and family functioning. Workplace stress's negative impact on family functioning dependent on individual's social identification level with their family group.

The aim of the study. To define the social identification's role for work and family life balance.

Materials and Methods

Data were collected from participants with the scales of multiple – choice questionnaire. The first scale that measured their workplace stress, participants were required to respond on questionnaire evaluated their feeling and thought during the last months at work. The second scale was about how participants perceive the quality of their family life. The last questionnaire was concerned with social identification with their family through scale that consists of three aspects of social identity, including ingroup ties, cognitive centrality and ingroup affect.

Types of scales are presented in Figure 1.

Workplace stress.

The workplace stress variable was measured by the Perceived Stress scale (PSS) that consists of 10 items (Cohen & Kamarck, 1994). They were asked questions (see Table 1), rating their feeling or thought in the last months at work in a certain way on a scale ranging from 0 to 4 (0 – never, 1 – almost never, 2 – sometimes, 3 – fairly often, 4 – very often).

Figure 1. Types of scales for measuring of workplace stress, family functioning, and social identification of participants.

Table 1. The questionnaire for measuring of workplace stress (by Cohen and Kamarck).

Questions	Coefficient alpha
How often were you being upset because of something that happened unexpectedly?	0.754
How often did you have a feeling that were unable to control the important things in life?	0.779
How often did you feel nervous and stressed?	0.786
How often did you find that could not cope with all the things that had to do?	0.780
How often were you angered because of things that happened that were outside of control?	0.795
How often did you feel difficulties were piling up so high that could not overcome them?	0.790
How often did you feel confident about your ability to handle personal problems?	0.789
How often did you have a feeling that things were going way?	0.787
How often were you able to control irritations in life?	0.824
How often did you feel that were on top of things?	0.783

Workplace stress was calculated by reversing the scores of the questions firstly, and then adding the scores for each item. Higher score indicated high level of perceived workplace stress. The reliability score for PSS in this study was $\alpha=0.805$.

Family functioning

Participants family functioning rate were measured by the Brief Family Relationship scale (BFFS) that was developed by Fok, Allen, Henry, and Team (2014). To measure participant’s perception of the quality of their family identification, they were asked to complete the questions (see Table 2) by rating with 4-point rating scales: 0 – strongly agree, 1 – agree, 2 – disagree, 3 – strongly disagree.

Lower score indicated the higher family functioning. In the present study a Cronbach alpha for BFFS was 0.905.

Social identification

The Three-Dimensional Strength of Group Identification scale is an instrument developed by Cameron (2004) that measured participant’s social identification level with their family. The scale consists of 12 items assessed participants 3 aspects of social identification: ingroup ties, cognitive centrality and ingroup affect. Responses are rated on 7 points rating scales from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree). The negative direct half of the items on the scale were required to reverse scoring before analysis. Higher scores indicated participant’s high social identification with their family. The Cronbach alpha coefficient for 12-item on the Three-Dimensional Strength of Group identification scale in the current study was 0.796.

Table 3 shows the Cronbach alpha coefficients for three scales.

Analyses of data

The hypotheses interaction between workplace stress and family functioning, social identification as a moderator for the association workplace stress with family functioning was analyzed by using Multiple linear regression analysis. The predictor variable was workplace stress and a moderator variable was social identification. These variables were manipulated with participants in the same groups. The dependent variable was a family functioning.

Procedure

Ethical approval of this study was gained from the Ethics Committee at the University of Exeter. They were informed about conducting research with university teachers about their work and family life. Before the completing data, participants were asked to read an information sheet with a consent form. They were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time. Furthermore, they receive instructions about their tasks during the study that would complete three types of questionnaires, which the time length for answering the questions of studies takes overall thirty minutes. In addition, they were informed via a consent form that there might be a few risk associated with the questionnaires for example, possible discomfort when answering some of the personal questions, and asked to sign the consent form whether they agreed to participate the study.

Table 2. The questionnaire for measuring of family functioning (by Fok, Allen, Henry, and Team).

Questions	Coefficient alpha
In our family we really help and support each other	0.889
In our family we spend a lot of time doing things together at home	0.900
In our family we work hard at what we do in our home	0.902
In our family there is a feeling of togetherness	0.890
My family members really support each other	0.886
I am proud to be a part of our family	0.885
In our family we really get along well with each other	0.879

Table 3. The Cronbach alpha coefficients for the scales.

Scales	Cronbach alpha
Perceived Stress Scale	0.805
Brief Family Relationship Scale	0.905
Three-Dimensional Strength of Group Identification Scale	0.796

Results

Testing the hypotheses showed that there was a positive correlation coefficient between workplace stress and family functioning ($r(82)=0.26, p<0.05$). The negative correlation coefficient suggested that increasing participant's social identification, might lower effect of workplace stress on their family functioning ($r(82)=-0.25, p<0.05$).

Testing the question whether the nature of the relationship between workplace stress and family functioning was changed through a function of social identification. Examining the moderation effect started with the value whether both workplace stress and a moderator variable had a significant effect on family functioning, and as results showed that workplace stress variable was not significantly predicted on family functioning in this model ($\beta=-0.57, t(79)=-6.19, p<0.05$) which suggested, social identification influences on decrease workplace stress's affect on family functioning.

Furthermore, there was a significant difference in workplace stress's impact on family functioning when the interaction term by social identification level was added. The workplace stress variable was not significant, with the interaction between high social identification and workplace stress included model ($\beta=-0.021, t(3.78)=-0.18, p=0.86$). When the interaction between low social identification and workplace stress was included in the model, workplace stress was significant ($\beta=0.41, t(3.78)=2.34, p=0.022$).

In addition, there was correlation between workplace stress and family functioning $r=0.60$, for the participants whose social identification with their family low. In contrast, a correlation coefficient between workplace stress and family functioning was reported $r=0.42$, for the people whose social identification with their family were high. It can be seen that, the coefficient of the interaction between social identification and workplace stress was statistically significant for the moderation of workplace stress's negative impact on family functioning. The coefficients with workplace stress were not significant when a high social identification variable was added to the model. However, workplace stress was a significant variable on family functioning, with the low social identification interaction term. Finally,

workplace stress's negative association with family functioning was dependent on individual's social identification level with their family members. Thus, predicting hypotheses were confirmed.

Discussion

Considering this, the result of the research conducting with participants – faculty members concluded that workplace stress had a direct negative effect on their family functioning. This supported analysis of qualitative questionnaire responses. It can be seen the results that individual's workplace stress's strong relation with their family might look as through their feelings, thoughts, moods and abilities to cope with workplace stressors. This was particularly clear in responses to questions about an inability to control important things in their life, and thought about something unexpected happening at work. This finding is consistent with a previous study by Wang, Repetti, and Campos (2011) that individual's workplace stress impacts on their family by their moods, thoughts, and coping behaviours. Participant's low family identification might appear as a decrease in a sense of supporting each other, spending less time together and a low feeling of togetherness.

This tendency might be reasoned by following factors: firstly, it would depend on their job type. In fact, there is a high demand for teaching at university, in spite of the average level of income. Mainly, faculty members have motivation to work an academic environment by their scientific interest. In addition, teacher's stress might be linked with their job conditions. Secondly, cultural differences of participants might be influential factors for their workplace stress which has impact on family functioning. In countries where the majority of the population is Muslim the female has a choice of about working, but they are responsible for family members 'caring, having children, organization family support, and consequently keeping family stability. In fact, female's work load may be divided into two parts depending on cultural differences, before and after marriage. Despite being a successful worker in education and academic fields, they prioritize their family conditions, but it is clear from previous findings females' role as a worker is also a significant factor for their work-life balance. This attitude might influence

individual's sensitivity to workplace stressors which are related to their family functioning.

However, there a high level of perceived stress indicated only among married female participants, excluding males. This finding contradicted the previous conclusion of Wang et al. (2001) that suggested men display more negative emotion as a result of workplace stress, report high neuroticism and express more active and more negative social behavior, but these patterns were not identified in women. However, the result has similarity with the Pennebaker's (1982) conclusion that women are more likely to report symptoms of physical and emotional discomfort than men. This could be participant's in particular, females' cultural, demographic features. Moreover, it probably impacts of their combination and attempt to satisfy two environment responsibilities. This result would be a significant factor for future research, as similarly Seiffge-Krenke, Aunola, and Nurmi (2009) study about changes in stress perception and coping suggested that for workplace stress perception situational factors are more impactful than the levels of perceived stress.

On the other hand, as Barnett and Baruch (1985) study concluded that working has play more significant effect to female that impacted on their family relationship than male. In contrast, Pleck (1985); Rosalind, Lois, and Grace (1987) both study suggested that men are more psychologically involved in their families than their work roles, and their well-being is dependent on family. Thus, workplace stress's impact on family functioning among female's were clear, whereas participant - male's workplace stress might be influenced by female's workplace stress's affect on their family relationship.

The Multiple linear regression analysis results showed that the direct effect of workplace stress on their family functioning reduced under the social identification's moderating condition. It is because social identification changes the mechanism depending on individual's social identification level with their family. In fact, the nature of the workplace stress's impact on family functioning changed as a result of the inclusion of interaction between social identification and workplace stress. This means, the effect of workplace stress to family functioning was not significant in the presence of individual's high level social identification with their family. It is because when individual's social identification with their family was high, their cognitive appraisal about family was central, and their ingroup ties affected among members of family that caused to decrease workplace stress's affect on family. For instance, when their ingroup ties increase, members of their families help and support each other, spend a lot of time doing things together at home, also work hard at what they do in their home. This feeling of togetherness might lead to them increasing their family ingroup effect that was expressed they were proud to be a part of their family; getting along well with each other members which consequently, guiding family as a central an individual's mind. Furthermore, cognitive appraisal is central to theories of psychological stress (Wang et al., 2011). Moreover, as outlined previous studies, when individuals perceive themselves as part of that group, increase the feeling that they are supported which has a

significant role for decreasing workplace stress's influence to family functioning (Haslam & Reicher, 2006).

In fact, there individual's whose social identification with their family was low, showed poor family relationship patterns, such as having difficulties to form a bond with other members, and decrease sense a family as a central part their self-image. Individual's social recourse from their family is a key variable in establishing their confidence in their ability to cope with stress (Klink, Byars-Winston, & Bakken, 2008). Because when members have identity and categorize as one group, this may influence their protecting group members from adverse reactions to strain and perceptions, increase a sense of support and responses for workplace stress (Haslam et al., 2005). Furthermore, social interaction might shape individual's psychological development by norms, roles and rules (1979) by reducing their stress. Previous finding by Haslam and Reicher (2006) claimed that when there is lower a sense of social identification among members of the group, this reduces the ability to resist the stressors. In addition, social identification variable interacts significantly with workplace stress on family functioning variable in the prediction of moderation for workplace stress effect, consistent with interactional model of personality theories (Endler & Magnusson, 1976). Consistent with such theories, 'actual behavior is determined by a continuous and multidirectional interaction between person variables and situation variables' (Magnusson & Endler, 1976) which means social identification with family as a situation and individual's responsibility to perceive and value family as centrality as personal variables play an important role changing stress.

The results of examination of workplace stress's negative association with family functioning, and social identification's role for workplace stress moderation concluded that the higher level of individual's social identification with their family, the lower negative effect from workplace stress on their family functioning. It is because when their sense of identity is high, they might influence others emotionally which gives them power to cope with stressors. Whereas negative social identification or poor relationship among members of family might a reason of workplace stress's significant impact on family functioning.

Conclusions

To conclude, workplace stress has a negative association with faculty member's family functioning. Individual's high social identification with their family is an effective coping method with workplace stress and, moderates the relationship between workplace stress and family functioning. Keeping faculty member's work and family life balance is dependent on their social identification level with family group.

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